

FURTHER IMPROVEMENT OF THE PRACTICE OF ASSET AND LIABILITY MANAGEMENT IN COMMERCIAL BANKS.

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Abstract: The purpose of scientific research. The purpose of the study is to consider the essence, role and methods of managing assets and liabilities of a commercial bank, analyze the financial condition of the bank, develop recommendations for improving the financial condition of the bank. Description of the scientific and practical significance of the work. The theoretical significance of the research results lies in clarifying the methods of analyzing the bank's assets and liabilities. The practical significance of the study lies in the fact that the conclusions, suggestions and recommendations formulated in the work are of a scientific and methodological nature and can be used to improve the efficiency of asset and liability management of a commercial bank.

Keywords: bank strategy, asset, liability, management, marketing, active, passive.

Introduction

A bank is a financial institution that serves to redistribute cash flows in the country. Any economy is based on objective economic laws, one of which is the law of monetary circulation. Money turnover occurs under the influence of financial institutions, and above all banks, which create the basis for money turnover and are connected with all branches and sectors of the economy. Banks provide financing for all spheres of entrepreneurship, production and non-production spheres, management spheres and fill the budget (both federal and territorial) with the necessary funds. Two-way movement of borrowed money (credit) is also carried out through banks.

The current state of the global financial system is characterized by many economists as a crisis. To date, the problem of ensuring the liquidity of commercial banks is one of the most important in the economic policy of developed countries. The Russian financial system has also faced certain difficulties, maintaining the necessary level of liquidity of the banking system is currently provided by the accumulated reserves of the state.

The analysis of banking activity, from the point of view of its profitability, allows the management to form a credit and interest rate policy, identify less profitable operations and develop recommendations for the possible receipt of large incomes. The solution of these tasks pursues the goal set before the management by the bank's shareholders: to improve the quality of assets, reduce the cost of liabilities and on this basis ensure capital growth and profit sufficient for the reproduction of banking activities and the payment of dividends. One of the most important conditions for the effective functioning of a market economy is the presence of a stable and actively working monetary system. Applying various methods of liquidity management, the credit institution seeks to find the most effective ratio of assets and liabilities that would provide the necessary level of profitability and would not jeopardize the bank's ability to meet its obligations[1].

Asset and liability management offers management tools and methods to solve these problems both at the level of management strategies, control over general banking operations, and at the level of management of various profit centers and even at the level of customer relations.

The bank's task is to attract resources that are optimal in terms of time and price, and place them in such a way as to cover the costs of attracting, while making a profit. The nature of banking activity determines the possibility of obtaining a large income and at the same time determines the presence of high risk. Taking into

account the bank's obligations to depositors, the bank's role in the economy, it is necessary to find a combination of active and passive operations that would reimburse costs, provide the necessary level of profitability and liquidity, compensate for risks, and the parameters of the bank's activities should comply with legally established standards.

In this paper, various approaches to liquidity management will be considered, involving both asset management and liability management.

The purpose of this work is to consider various approaches to managing the liquidity of a commercial bank.

To achieve the goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

- * to reveal the content of the concept of liquidity;
- * consider the content of the concepts of assets and liabilities of a commercial bank in modern economic theory;
- * to study the factors affecting the liquidity of a commercial bank;
- * disclose the content of the main methods of liquidity management;
- * consider asset and liability management methods.

The object of the study is various methods of managing the liquidity, assets and liabilities of a commercial bank. The subject of the study is the theoretical foundations of each method.

The theoretical and informational base of the work is the normative legal acts of the Central Bank of the Russian Federation, materials of various textbooks.

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